

Attribute Management in SGIS Desktop v1.2: Joining Multiple Attribute Fields from Multiple Tables Derived from Various CAD Layers

Elena Gjorgjieva; Kiro Gjorgjiev

elena@simplegissoft.com ; kiro@simplegissoft.com ; info@simplegissoft.com

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Joining multiple attribute fields from different tables and CAD layers in GIS is essential for effective data integration and analysis. It allows users to combine diverse datasets, enabling more comprehensive spatial queries, visualizations, and decision-making.

This guide provides a step-by-step walkthrough to help users understand how to complete this task in SGIS. We're using a real-world scenario provided by a user, which means the data hasn't been cleaned, giving us the opportunity to explore all the steps together. Using real-life data offers a clearer understanding of the process and better demonstrates the software's capabilities. So let's get started!

First, we open the DXF file.

Fig.1 Loading a DXF file into SGIS Desktop v1.2.

Fig.2 The DXF file loads three layers: polygon, polyline, and point, which need to be unpacked to reveal the original CAD layers.

Once the DXF file is loaded, three layers will be displayed in the Layers panel: a polygon layer, a polyline layer, and a point layer. To access the original CAD data, we need to unpack these layers, allowing the original CAD layers to appear in the layer list.

To do this, we click on the 'Separate GIS layers by DXF layers' function.

Fig.3 Each layer is selected and unpacked sequentially: first the polygon, then the polyline, and finally the point layer.

We start by selecting the first layer and unpacking it. Next, we activate the second layer and repeat the process, followed by the third layer.

Fig.4 After unpacking, the original CAD layers appear in the Layers Panel, while the initial three are unchecked, showing they are empty. GIS layers are labeled by feature type.

Once all three layers are unpacked, the original CAD layers will appear in the Layers Panel, with the initial three layers now unchecked, indicating that they are empty. To maintain clarity, the newly created GIS layers from the CAD data retain names that specify whether they contain polygon features, polyline features, or points. Their visual properties are carried over from the original CAD layer, though these can be adjusted later if needed.

Fig.5 Deleting the initial three empty layers and checking for any other unnecessary layers to remove.

Fig.6 Converting the two polyline features into polygons while one polygon feature is already correctly displayed.

The original layer has three shape features that should be polygons. One of these is already a polygon, shown as a yellow polygon in the graphics panel. The other two are polylines, which we will now convert into polygons.

Fig.7 Clicking on 'Close Polylines' converts the selected polyline into a polygon.

To enhance clarity, we first turn off the polygon layer and select one of the polyline layers from the Layers panel. Then, we click on 'Close Polylines,' which converts the polyline into a polygon. This action creates a new polygon layer in the list while keeping the original polyline layer unchanged.

Fig.8 The new polygon layer is added to the list, while the original polyline layer remains unchanged.

Fig.9 Clicking 'Close Polylines' to convert the second polyline into a polygon.

We follow the same steps to convert the second polyline into a polygon. Once this is done, we'll arrange the three polygon layers in the Layers panel and organize the point layers as well. We have four point layers, which were labels in the CAD file. Each label includes an attribute field named TEXT, which contains the original label information once imported into the GIS environment. To combine fields from these four different CAD-originated layers, we need to check which point layer has the most point features.

Fig.10 Arranging the three polygon layers and organizing the point layers in the Layers panel.

We need to do this because we've observed that the points overlap but don't all have values for every coordinate. For instance, all points are labeled as "Residen," but some also include additional labels like house numbers or street names. These additional labels overlap with each other, which is why we need to examine and manage the point layers carefully.

Fig.11 Checking the number of elements in the 'Street Name' layer, which contains 458 items.

To begin, we check the number of elements in the first point layer. We do this by clicking on 'Attribute' to open the attribute table. In the info bar, we can see the layer name, which in this case is 'Street Name,' along with the number of elements it contains. Here, we see that the layer has 458 elements.

Fig.12 Checking the 'House Number' point layer, which contains 307 elements.

We repeat the process with the second point layer, 'House Number,' which contains 307 elements.

Fig.13 Checking the third point layer, 'Residen,' which contains 685 elements.

We check the third layer, named 'Residen,' and find that it contains 685 elements. Finally, we check the fourth point layer, 'Business.' This layer has the fewest elements, with only 19 compared to the others.

Fig.14 Checking the final point layer, 'Business,' which contains 19 elements, the fewest among all layers.

Fig.15 Arranging layers in the Layers panel from highest to lowest based on the number of elements: 'Residen' at the top, followed by 'Street Name,' 'House Number,' and 'Business' at the bottom.

Using the 'Up' and 'Down' functions, we'll arrange the layers in the Layers panel, with the layer containing the most elements positioned at the top. In this example, the order will be: first 'Residen,' followed by 'Street Name,' then 'House Number,' and finally 'Business'.

Before using the 'Link Data' tool from the Attribute Tools, we need to make some minor edits to the attribute table in the 'Residen' layer.

Fig.16 Editing the attribute table in the 'Residen' layer is necessary before using the 'Link Data' tool.

Fig.17 The 'Link Data' settings dialog is open, but we'll exit for now to edit and clean the attribute table in the Residen layer before returning to this tool.

After clicking the 'Link Attributes' tool, a dialog window will open. In this window, we'll need to adjust the settings for the process to work correctly. We'll choose a field from the dropdown list that will be modified.

Since the attribute table in the 'Residen' layer still contains the original fields from the CAD import, we'll need to make some edits to this table first. So, we'll exit the 'Link Data' dialog for now and return to it once we've completed the necessary modifications to the 'Residen' attribute table.

Fig.18 Renaming the 'Text' field to 'Residen' and deleting the other fields.

First, we click on the 'Attribute Fields' tool to open a window for editing attribute fields. Here, we can rename existing fields, delete unnecessary ones, and add new fields as needed.

In this case, we need to rename the field named 'Text' to 'Residen' because it holds the Residen values from the CAD labels. We'll then delete the other fields, create new ones for 'Street Name,' 'House Numbers,' and 'Business'.

Fig.19 Using the 'Add Field' function in the 'Attribute Fields' tool to create new fields.

Fig.20 After creating the necessary fields, we click 'Save' to apply the changes.

Fig.21 Viewing the updated Attribute Table, where the "Text" field is now renamed "Residen" and the new fields remain empty.

We can now open the Attribute Table to review the changes.

The field previously named "Text" is now labeled "Residen" and is populated with values, while the newly created fields remain empty.

Now that we've made the necessary changes, we can move forward by opening the 'Link Data' tool from the Attribute Table. We simply click on the function to begin.

Fig.22 Opening the 'Link Data' tool after completing the attribute table modifications.

In this dialog window, there are a few important elements to explain. First, the active layer is displayed as 'Point_Residen,' which cannot be changed once the window is opened, so it appears inactive.

Fig.23 Setting the active layer, selecting the field to update, and linking data from the 'point_StreetName' layer with a 0.25m tolerance radius.

Below that, there's a dropdown list where we need to select the field we want to update—in our case, it's the 'Street Name' field. Since our points overlap and match geometrically, we'll leave the 'Relation' field as 'Points Match.'

In the upper right, we select the layer from which to extract the data, so we choose the 'point_StreetName' layer, and the field to pull data from is 'TEXT.' We leave the remaining settings empty but set the tolerance radius to 0.25m. Finally, we click 'Link Data'.

Fig.24 The Info bar confirms "Link Data processing is complete," with details in the Memo box showing the number of updated elements. Users can save this information as a LOG file by right-clicking in the box.

In the Info bar, we see the message "Link Data processing is complete." Below, the Memo box shows how many elements were updated. Users can right-click inside the box to save this information as a LOG file if needed.

Fig.25 The memo box showing the count of elements that have been updated.

Fig.26 Opening the attribute table to verify if all data has been correctly linked and connected.

After completing the procedure, we open the attribute table to check if all the data is correctly linked and connected.

Fig.27 Adding new columns for X and Y coordinates using the 'Attribute Fields' tool.

We need to add two more columns for X and Y coordinates. We'll do this using the same procedure in the 'Attribute Fields' tool. Once the changes are saved, we'll open the attribute table again, and you'll see that these new columns are empty.

We'll need to fill in these values.

Fig.28 Use the 'Fill Field with X Coordinate' and 'Fill Field with Y Coordinate' functions to populate the X and Y columns with coordinate values.

To populate these columns, right-click on a cell in the X or Y column. Then select 'Fill Field with X Coordinate' for the X column and 'Fill Field with Y Coordinate' for the Y column, respectively.

Fig.29 The X and Y columns are filled with their respective coordinate values.

With the X and Y columns now filled with their respective values, the procedure is complete. To save these changes to the attribute table, we click on 'Save'. A confirmation message will appear asking if we're sure we want to save the changes. We click 'Yes' to confirm.

Fig.30 Saving the updated attribute table after filling in the X and Y coordinate columns.

Fig.31 Export attributes as a text file by navigating to the Element Data toolbox and selecting 'Export Attributes to CSV'.

The final step is to export the attribute table as a text file so users can process their data further. In SGIS, you can do this in two ways; Use the 'Export Attributes to CSV' function in the Element Data toolbox. Or, open the Attribute Table again, go to the Attribute Table tools ribbon, and choose 'Save attributes as text file'. This will allow you to export the file as either a .txt or .csv file format. And with that, the procedure is complete.

Fig.32 Alternatively, open the Attribute Table, go to the Attribute Table tools ribbon, and select 'Save attributes as text file' to export the file as a .txt or .csv format.